

Expanding Integrated Assessment Modelling:
Comprehensive and Comprehensible Science
for Sustainable, Co-Created Climate Action

D1.4 – Report on Project and SAB Meetings – Update 1

WP1 – Project Management

30/08/2024

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This report can be used for internally reviewing the project's progress from September 2023 till August 2024, and as a reference point for project partners on the completion of their tasks regarding the agreed conditions by the consortium.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

In accordance with the project's Quality Management Plan, remote (online) and physical meetings (in hybrid format) are taking place so that consortium partners communicate and cooperate during the IAM COMPACT project's lifetime. In this context, monthly Executive Board Meetings are arranged online through Microsoft Teams as well as biannual General Assembly Meetings, which are hosted either back-to-back with other physical events organised by the project or held online. The monthly meetings aim to update all consortium members on the progress of all Work Packages, maintain all actions within the agreed timelines, and ensure that corrective actions (if needed) are taken in due time. Thus, these monthly meetings contribute to achieving the project's goals and vision. NTUA's administration team is organising these meetings and proposes the agenda in advance, before finalising it with all partners.

In the second year of the project (September 2023 – August 2024), no physical meetings were organised for sustainability reasons and to align with the overall work programme. The third General Assembly of the project took place on the 26th and 27th of February 2024 (online), as well as 6 Executive Board Meetings, all through Microsoft Teams. All meetings were characterised by high levels of participation from all partners (European and international as well), with everyone demonstrating significant commitment to the project's goals.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report is evidence for the realisation of the project's meetings as they are presented in the Grant Agreement. Moreover, the implementation of the actions discussed in these meetings is and/or will be demonstrated in the rest of the project's deliverables, which inter alia report the significant research work carried out in IAM COMPACT.

Preface

IAM COMPACT supports the assessment of global climate goals, progress, and feasibility space, and the design of the next round of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and policy planning beyond 2030 for major emitters and non-high-income countries. It uses a diverse ensemble of models, tools, and insights from social and political sciences and operations research, integrating bodies of knowledge to co-create the research process and enhance transparency, robustness, and policy relevance. It explores the role of structural changes in major emitting sectors and of political, behaviour, and social aspects in mitigation, quantifies factors promoting or hindering climate neutrality, and accounts for extreme scenarios, to deliver a range of global and national pathways that are environmentally effective, viable, feasible, and desirable. In doing so, it fully accounts for COVID-19 impacts and recovery strategies and aligns climate action with broader sustainability goals, while developing technical capacity and promoting ownership in non-high-income countries.

NTUA – National Technical University of Athens	EL	
Aalto – Aalto Korkeakoulusaatio SR	FI	
AAU – Aalborg Universitet	DK	
BC3 – Asociacion BC3 Basque Centre for Climate Change – Klima Aldaketa Ikergai	ES	
Bruegel – Bruegel AISBL	BE	
CARTIF – Fundacion CARTIF	ES	
CICERO – Cicero Senter for Klimaforskning Stiftelse	NO	
E3M – E3-Modelling AE	EL	
KTH – Kungliga Tekniska Hoegskolan	SE	
POLIMI – Politecnico di Milano	IT	
UPRC – University of Piraeus Research Center	EL	
UVa – Universidad De Valladolid	ES	
WI – Wuppertal Institut fur Klima, Umwelt, Energie GGMBH	DE	
IIMA – Indian Institute of Management	IN	
THU – Tsinghua University	CN	
USMF – University System of Maryland	US	
AAiT – Addis Ababa University	ET	
KEI – International Civic Organisation Kyiv Economics Institute	UA	
RUSL – Raja Rata University of Sri Lanka	LK	
TUM – Technical University of Mombasa	KE	
UNIGE – Université de Genève	CH	
Imperial – Imperial College of Science, Technology and Medicine	UK	

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1 Introduction

According to the Grant Agreement, both regular and ad-hoc meetings are held throughout the project’s duration. Regular meetings, known as General Assembly meetings, are scheduled biannually to review the progress of all activities and help partners understand, follow, and contribute to the comprehensive scientific work conducted within the project. NTUA is responsible for setting the agenda, organising these meetings (in collaboration with other partners), and sharing the details of the meeting time and location. In addition, online meetings via Microsoft Teams are held regularly to discuss specific issues related to project deliverables and tasks. NTUA also arranges monthly Executive Board Meetings to ensure all partners are aligned with the project’s progress and activities. NTUA records all meetings and sessions related to project management, coordination, and other work packages. Although the consortium holds dozens of ad hoc meetings related to specific WPs, tasks, or even activities/events, this deliverable specifically pertains to the regular General Assembly and Executive Board Meetings, for which the NTUA administration team takes minutes and promptly distributes them to all partners, ensuring that the entire consortium is updated on the project’s progress, actions, plans, and timelines.

The following table lists the meetings that took place during the second year of the project. Executive Board meetings take place on a monthly basis, meaning once every month—unless a General Assembly is scheduled for the same month (hence, no Executive Board meeting was held in February 2024) or due to unavailability in holiday seasons (hence, no Executive Board meetings took place in December 2023, May 2024, July 2024, and August 2024).

Table 1. IAM COMPACT Project Meetings (covering period September 2023 – August 2024)

Type of meeting		Date
Online	Executive Board Meeting	31 st of October 2023
Online	Executive Board Meeting	28 th of November 2023
Online	Executive Board Meeting	16 th of January 2024
Online	3 rd General Assembly Meeting	26 th and 27 th of February 2024
Online	Executive Board Meeting	28 th of March 2024
Online	Executive Board Meeting	23 rd of April 2024
Online	Executive Board Meeting	18 th of June 2024

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This deliverable aims to capture a periodic account of all project meetings, including the meetings’ agenda, attendance, and minutes. It also aims to report any feedback from the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) from any online communication, especially in the context of dedicated SAB meetings, typically taking place during General Assembly meetings.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The deliverable is separated into two sections. Section 2 presents the agenda and minutes of the online meetings and Section 3 describes the feedback provided by the project’s SAB.

2 Remote (Online) Meetings

2.1 Executive Board Meeting – 31 October 2023

2.1.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Tuesday, 31 October, 2023
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Project Management
 - First year stocktake: M1 – M12
 - Second year overview: M13 – M24
 - WP2: Listening
 - Core Working Groups – update on the completion of EU workshops and on the progress in regional events (Bruegel)
 - WP3: Exchanging
 - D3.2: Open data management plan – December 2023 (Imperial)
 - WP4: Modelling
 - First modelling cycle: PRM1 Studies progress (Imperial & Study leads)
 - D4.5: National, regional, global mitigation pathways – November 2023 (Imperial)
 - D4.7: Sectoral and cross-sectoral analysis – December 2023 (WI)
 - WP5: Expanding
 - COVID-19 analysis (Task 5.1): progress (E3M)
 - Distributional impacts (Task 5.2): progress (BC3)
 - WP6: Explaining
 - Task 6.1 – CDE progress so far (UPRC)
 - Task 6.3 – ECEMP (completed), IAMC (upcoming), etc (NTUA)
 - Tasks 6.4-6.5 coordination (KTH, WI), including:
 - Drivers and barriers analysis (WI, sector study leads)
 - Progress with regard to Ukraine, Sri Lanka, Ethiopia workshops (KTH, KEI, RUSL, AAiT)

2. Any other business**2.1.2 Minutes**

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	NTUA
2	Anastasios Karamaneas	NTUA
3	Natasha Frilingou	NTUA
4	Konstantinos Koasidis	NTUA
5	Ilkka Keppo	Aalto
6	Hesam Ghadaksaz	Aalto
7	Rasmus Magni Johanssen	AAU
8	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
9	Jon Sampedro	BC3
10	Claudia Rodés	BC3
11	Conall Heussaff	Bruegel
12	Adrian Lauer	Bruegel
13	Georg Zachmann	Bruegel
14	Adrián Mateo Martínez	CARTIF
15	Noelia Ferreras Alonso	CARTIF
16	Glen Peters	CICERO
17	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
18	Eleftheria Zisarou	E3M
19	Panagiotis Fragkos	E3M
20	Eftychia Ntostoglou	KTH
21	Fumi Maeda Harapap	KTH
22	Francesco Gardumi	KTH
23	Lorenzo Rinaldi	POLIMI
24	Nikolaos Kleanthis	UPRC
25	Sophia Theodoropoulou	UPRC
26	Jaime Nieto	UVa
27	Solomon Teferi	AAiT
28	Ioannis Tsiouridis	TUM
29	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
30	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
31	Alaa Al Khourdajie	Imperial

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	The meeting started with Dr Alexandros Nikas (NTUA) greeting the consortium. Then, he informed the partners about the project's side event in COP-28, where a study published in the <i>Joule</i> journal will be presented. This study examines the EU's path to net zero and specifically its interim targets. In this side event Dr Alaa Al Khourdajie (Imperial) will present the role of CCS and Prof Steve Pye from UCL, representing the EU HORIZON DIAMOND project will present the role of natural gas. Prof Haris Doukas (NTUA) will also participate in this event. Moreover, partners from THU and UMD will also be there. Lastly, regarding this matter, Dr Nikas mentioned that the Greek Ministry of Environment and Energy focuses on EU perspectives, wants an in-	Organise the COP-28 side event	NTUA, Imperial

	<p>person event and they suggested that a moderator from the ministry participates as well.</p> <p>Next, Dr Nikas informed the consortium that Prof Doukas was recently elected Mayor of the Municipality of Athens, hence a different project coordinator will have to be appointed, but apart from that, no major disruptions are expected due to this news.</p> <p>Moreover, Dr Nikas stressed that the following 3-4 months will require a lot of work since most of the modelling activities will kick off and Deliverables D4.5 and D4.7 will have to be updated.</p> <p>Lastly, Dr Nikas mentioned that the Core Working Group meetings had just ended with a high level of participation.</p>		
WP2	<p>Next, Mr. Conall Heussaff (Bruegel) took the floor and briefed the partners on the thematic sections of the Core Working Groups. He also mentioned that they provided useful insights. Then, he mentioned that the Kenyan stakeholder activities are completed and that the workshops for 6 more countries are scheduled to take place. The workshops for India, China and the USA will take place until the end of December 2023, whereas the stakeholder events for Sri Lanka, Ethiopia and Ukraine until the end of January 2024. Lastly, Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) suggested that there is a request to examine SSP data since there are some divergencies, with Mr. Heussaff replying that this issue can be discussed in the national workshops.</p>	Organise the 6 countries workshops	Bruegel, regional partners
WP3	<p>Regarding WP3, Dr Mittal mentioned that the OPEN database is scheduled to be updated with data such as the SSP scenarios</p>	OPEN database update	Imperial
WP4	<p>Next, Ms. Natasha Frilingou (NTUA) took the floor and briefed the partners on the stakeholder feedback on Study 6 regarding interest rates. She mentioned that their answers matched the project's already-designed scenarios.</p> <p>Afterwards, Ms. Eleftheria Zisarou (E3M) mentioned that there was a good level of participation in the workshop for Study 3, which focused on batteries.</p> <p>Regarding Study 7, Prof Jaime Nieto (Uva) mentioned that there was a high level of engagement with the questions posed and that it is tricky to translate some of the stakeholders' requests into the project's models. In this context, Dr Nikas added that there was a high level of participation.</p> <p>Next, Dr Mittal mentioned that there are already some results from Study 1.</p> <p>Moreover, she mentioned that GCAM has already provided useful information and that she expects to have some first results for Study 1 in a couple of weeks.</p> <p>Last, Dr Panagiotis Fragkos informed the consortium that this week a meeting will take place in order to finalise the protocol for Study 3, with Dr Mittal adding that this work is part of D5.3.</p>	Continue the work on the 7 studies	All partners involved in the studies
WP5	<p>Next, Dr Fragkos proceeded to WP5, mentioning that the E3M team is already working on some deliverables and modelling scenarios as well as on some macroeconomic models together with BC3. He also mentioned that there is already a book chapter published relating to D5.2. Afterwards, he informed the partners that Prof Evelina Trutnevyte (UNIGE) had already made a structure for D5.3. He also mentioned that work on the sustainability-related deliverable has also commenced. Then, Dr Nikas added that the final study is not within the 1st Reporting Period. Lastly, Ms. Frilingou mentioned that CARTIF partners have</p>	Prepare a list of the SDGs that each model can proxy	All modelling partners

	asked for a list including the SDGs that each model can proxy.		
WP6	<p>Next, Ms. Sophia Theodoropoulou (UPRC) took the floor and briefed the consortium on the CDE indicators. Specifically, she mentioned that the project’s website should aim to increase its visitors. On the other hand, the project is demonstrating great progress regarding its social media accounts, its video performance as well as its scientific publications. Lastly, she mentioned that the consortium should prepare the training material kits and publish them. In this context, Dr Francesco Gardumi (KTH) replied that the 1st batch will be available in February 2024.</p> <p>Next, Dr Nikas took the floor, regarding Task 6.3, for which he mentioned that the consortium’s presence at the ECMP conference was successful with 2 presentations representing the project (a <i>Joule</i> paper and the energy crisis paper). In this context, he also mentioned that partners from the consortium chaired a session on multi-model assessments. Moreover, he mentioned that the project will also have significant participation in the IAMC conference in Venice with 6 papers/posters and he suggested that the partners attending the conference meet each other.</p> <p>Then, he mentioned that a meeting for Tasks 6.4 and 6.5 will take place the following week. In this context, regarding Task 6.4, Ms. Eftychia Ntostoglou (KTH) mentioned that a further iteration is completed, and the country sheets will be finalised in the following December.</p> <p>Next, Dr Fumi Harahap (KTH) took the floor and informed the consortium that the model framework is being finalised and that a capacity development workshop will take place in Ethiopia in early January 2024, in a hybrid format so stakeholders can participate physically and project partners being able to participate online. She also mentioned that KTH and AAiT partners are already communicating for a possible meeting in mid-November.</p> <p>Afterwards, Ms. Ntostoglou mentioned that an online workshop for Sri Lanka will also take place in January 2024, and KTH is discussing the details with Prof Lahiru Jayasuriya (RUSL).</p> <p>Next, Dr Gardumi informed the partners that KTH has been discussing with Dr Borys Dodonov (KSE) about a potential date for the 1st workshop on Ukraine, to take place on the 23rd and 24th of November but that they are still waiting for a reply from the Ukrainian Ministry of Energy. An OSeMOSYS model for Ukraine will be developed, drawing data from a previous TIMES model, chosen for easier capacity development activities, focusing on its newly developed interface.</p> <p>Moreover, Prof Ioannis Tsipouridis (TUM) informed the consortium that the stakeholder engagement activities in Kenya went well, with a good level of attendance from students. He also mentioned that they are preparing a CLEWs modelling class, the preparation of which will be supported by Dr Gardumi. He mentioned that he hopes the class will start the following January.</p> <p>Next, Ms. Ntostoglou mentioned that KTH is putting together the training material from Kenya for the MS6 report and Dr Gardumi added that the modelling material will be further enhanced after the 1st batch is published.</p> <p>Lastly, Dr Nikas expressed his satisfaction that all workshops will be hybrid and thanked everyone for their attendance at this</p>	<p>Prepare the 1st batch of training material</p> <p>Organise the Ethiopia, Sri Lanka and Ukraine workshops</p>	<p>KTH</p> <p>KTH, AAiT, RUSL, KEI</p>

	meeting.		
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2.2 Executive Board Meeting – 28 November 2023

2.2.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Tuesday, 28 November, 2023
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Project Management
 - I2AM PARIS v2.0 - January 2024 (NTUA)
 - Next GA meeting (February or March 2024)
 - Midterm report & review meeting
 - WP2: Listening
 - Core Working Groups –progress on regional events (Bruegel)
 - Any info needed for D2.4: Proceedings of Stakeholder
 - Stakeholder interactions - January 2024 (Bruegel)
 - WP3: Exchanging
 - D3.2: Open data management plan – December 2023 (Imperial)
 - WP4: Modelling
 - First modelling cycle: PRM1 Studies progress (Imperial & Study leads)
 - D4.5: National, regional, global mitigation pathways – November 2023 (Imperial)
 - D4.7: Sectoral and cross-sectoral analysis – December 2023 (WI)
 - D4.9: European sub-national deep dives – January 2024 (UNIGE)
 - WP5: Expanding
 - D5.1: Impact assessment of COVID-19 recovery COVID-19 analysis – January 2024 (E3M)
 - Task 5.2- Distributional impacts: progress (BC3)
 - Task 5.6 – SDG mapping progress (CARTIF, NTUA)
 - WP6: Explaining
 - Task 6.1 – CDE progress so far (UPRC)
 - Task 6.2 – PRM1 policy brief (Bruegel)
 - Task 6.3 –IAMC (completed), COP28 (upcoming) (NTUA)
 - Tasks 6.4-6.5 coordination (KTH, WI), including:
 - Drivers and barriers analysis (WI, sector study leads)

- Progress with regard to Ukraine, Sri Lanka, Ethiopia workshops (KTH, KEI, RUSL, AAiT)

2. Any other business

2.2.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	NTUA
2	Anastasios Karamaneas	NTUA
3	Natasha Frilingou	NTUA
4	Konstantinos Koasidis	NTUA
5	Thomas Nikolakakis	NTUA
6	Ilkka Keppo	Aalto
7	Rasmus Magni Johanssen	AAU
8	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
9	Russell Horowitz	BC3
10	Claudia Rodés	BC3
11	Conall Heussaff	Bruegel
12	Adrián Mateo Martínez	CARTIF
13	Noelia Ferreras Alonso	CARTIF
14	Glen Peters	CICERO
15	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
16	Eleftheria Zisarou	E3M
17	Panagiotis Fragkos	E3M
18	Anastasis Giannousakis	E3M
19	Eftychia Ntostoglou	KTH
20	Francesco Gardumi	KTH
21	Nikolaos Kleanthis	UPRC
22	Sophia Theodoropoulou	UPRC
23	Jaime Nieto	UVa
24	Dagmar Kigar	WI
25	Lena Tholen	WI
26	Jyoti Maheshwari	IIMA
27	John Maitha Thoya	TUM
28	Salsabila Abdulhalim	TUM
29	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
30	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
31	Alaa Al Khourdajie	Imperial

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	The meeting commenced with Dr Alexandros Nikas (NTUA) greeting the consortium and informing them that Prof Haris Doukas (NTUA), the project's coordinator, was recently elected mayor of Athens, hence from the 1 st of January 2024 he will not be able to be the project's coordinator, meaning that Dr Nikas will take this responsibility, assuring that no changes will take place in the way that the project is managed. Dr Nikas also mentioned that no amendment will be needed and that the Project Officer is informed of this issue. Next, Dr Nikas expressed his happiness for the project's great	Submit papers to the EGU conference Determine the days that the GA meeting will take place Set up a <i>Doodle</i>	All partners NTUA NTUA

	<p>representation in the IAMC conference with more than 7 presentations, which was a big success. In this context, he also encouraged the project's partners to submit their work, acknowledging the project, at the EGU conference, in which a session will be held by project partners. He also encouraged the consortium to communicate with him and Ms. Natasha Frilingou (NTUA) if they need further information.</p> <p>Afterwards, he informed the partners that the updated version of the I²AM PARIS platform would be available in the following January.</p> <p>The next matter discussed was the organisation of the upcoming General Assembly (GA) meeting, which would be taking place in the second half of the following February. In this context, Dr Nikas requested that all partners fill in the <i>Doodle</i> poll expressing their availability, intending to ensure that all partners can participate with at least one member of their team. Adding to that, Ms. Frilingou suggested that communication with CICERO partners should take place to ensure that the GA meeting does not take place on a Norwegian national holiday at the same period, with Prof Ilkka Keppo (Aalto) stating that the same national holiday is also celebrated in Finland. In this respect, Dr Nikas mentioned that the last week of February seems more convenient and that the exact days would be determined the following week. Additionally, he indicated that a <i>Doodle</i> poll will take place to investigate the best one-hour slot for the SAB session during the 2-day meeting. Regarding the focal areas of the GA meeting, Dr Nikas mentioned that part of the GA meeting will be devoted to delivering everything requested in the 1st Reporting Period as well as the Interim Report, hence financial issues will also be discussed. In this context, he assured the consortium that the NTUA administration team would provide partners with a template demonstrating all the necessary information that should be filled in for each WP. Furthermore, he requested that all partners propose what they deem necessary to be discussed for each WP in the upcoming GA meeting within December so the agenda can be formulated before Christmas. In this context, Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) suggested that some time should be allocated to discuss modelling results as well as policies mapping stakeholder engagement, with Dr Nikas commenting that stakeholders should be engaged prior to the upcoming GA meeting. Then, Dr Mittal and Mr Conall Heussaff (Bruegel) discussed the stakeholder meetings and their timeline, with Mr Heussaff stating that the format of the 2nd round of stakeholder meetings should also be investigated during the upcoming GA. Dr Nikas added that focus should also be given to the impact of the RPM on the 2nd round of stakeholder meetings. He also indicated that the consortium should communicate with the Core Working Groups to get their feedback by the following February.</p> <p>In a different context, Dr Nikas informed the consortium that the Project Advisor had asked to have a review meeting by the following May and then he briefed the partners on the review process (technical reports etc.) focusing on the mid-term report process. Respectively, Dr Nikas and Dr Mittal discussed about UK partners not being obliged to submit a financial report. Moreover, Dr Francesco Gardumi (KTH) asked if there is some template for these procedures, with Dr Nikas proposing to share an example</p>	<p>poll for the SAB session</p> <p>Communicate with NTUA administration about what should be discussed in the upcoming GA meeting</p> <p>Communicate with CWG to receive feedback</p> <p>Arrange a review meeting with the PO</p>	<p>All partners</p> <p>NTUA, Bruegel</p> <p>NTUA</p>
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	<p>from a previous project. He also stressed the need to pinpoint all WP meetings in the Interim Report with a short description for each meeting. Lastly, Ms. Sophia Theodoropoulou (UPRC) mentioned that UPRC is using a template for pinpointing meetings, with Dr Nikas replying that this might be useful for all partners.</p>		
WP2	<p>The discussion on WP2 started with Mr Heussaff taking the floor, mentioning that the consortium has further proceeded on the 1st iteration of the 1st RPM cycle, with the India, US and China workshops having taken place already. In this context, Dr Mittal requested that feedback from these workshops be distributed. Then, Mr Heussaff mentioned that the Ukraine, Sri Lanka and Ethiopia workshops will take place in the following January, providing enough time to include their feedback in the reports of the 1st Reporting Period.</p> <p>Next, he mentioned that they are preparing D2.4 regarding the PRM processes and their first results, which is due the following January, with Dr Nikas stating that partners should not be concerned about potential overlaps occurring in the 1st Reporting Period reports.</p> <p>Lastly, Dr Mittal and Mr Heussaff mentioned that some initial modelling results from India, the USA and China are expected to be produced by January 2024 for D2.5.</p>	<p>Prepare D2.4</p> <p>Produce initial modelling results for India, the USA and China</p>	<p>Bruegel</p> <p>IIMA, UMD, THU, Imperial</p>
WP3	<p>Next, Dr Nikas informed the consortium that the only major update regarding WP3 is the Open Data Management Plan which must be submitted by the following January. In this context, Dr Mittal and Dr Gardumi discussed the protocols of the models used in WP6, with Dr Gardumi stating that these are open models, with open-access data (some data may not be available for sharing due to stakeholder denial) and with training materials with a CC BY 4.0 license. A Milestone report will be prepared by February 2024 for this material, which will be updated until the end of the project. In this respect, Dr Mittal requested a short description of the models' licenses.</p>	<p>Submit the Open Data Management Plan</p> <p>Prepare the MS report on training materials</p>	<p>NTUA</p> <p>KTH</p>
WP4	<p>Following, Dr Mittal proceeded to WP4 summarising the progress of the 7 studies, focusing on studies 1,2,4 and 6. Next, she presented the process overview of D4.5 which will be submitted in two phases, with the second one including updated results. Then, she presented the content and timeline of D4.7 which is also separated into two phases, which must be followed by a submission in the following December and February respectively. Afterwards, she proceeded to the schematic overview of Study 4, focusing on the interlinkages of models.</p> <p>Dr Nikas took the floor mentioning that a preliminary version of D4.5 is already being reviewed. He also informed the consortium that the paper on the energy crisis must be revised with the revision comments being characterised as manageable. Lastly, he mentioned that there must be a discussion with the Project Officer regarding the disclosure of some deliverables in order to avoid self-plagiarism.</p>	<p>Submission of D4.7</p>	<p>Imperial</p>
WP5	<p>Next, Dr Panagiotis Fragkos (E3M) informed the consortium that the harmonisation database has been prepared and then proceeded to summarise the progress on each task. Regarding Task 5.1 he mentioned that the E3M team is working on modelling and aim to deliver by the mid of December 2023. Afterwards, he mentioned that leading the work of Task 5.2 is divided between</p>	<p>Prepare D5.1</p>	<p>E3M</p>

	<p>BC3 and E3M working on two studies regarding decarbonisation's social aspects and the impact of the energy transition on Greek household income respectively. The second study has already been published as a book chapter. Concerning Task 5.3, he mentioned that E3M is leading a study focusing on material interlinkages, in which the MARIO model will be used. Task 5.4 is led by Imperial, focusing on the contribution of immature technologies. Lastly, regarding Task 5.6, Dr Fragkos informed the consortium that a review of SDGs covered by each model will be conducted by NTUA and Uva.</p>		
WP6	<p>Ms. Theodoropoulou took the floor, informing the partners that there is no major update regarding CDE activities planning and suggested sharing the CDE progress presentation with the consortium due to limited time during this meeting.</p> <p>Next, Dr Nikas mentioned that on the 5th of December 2023, a side event in COP28 will take place, presenting the results of an IAM COMPACT paper featured in the <i>Joule</i> journal.</p> <p>Afterwards, Ms. Eftychia Ntostoglou (KTH) briefed the consortium on the workshops' status, mentioning that there is a relevant presentation in the project's repository, available for all partners. Specifically, she indicated that the Ethiopian workshop will take place on the 23rd and the 24th of January 2024 and that the Ukraine and Sri Lanka workshops will also take place in January, with their exact dates to be shortly determined. She also expressed KTH's efforts not to overlap these workshops and also to accommodate as many stakeholders as possible at the same time. Moreover, she mentioned that update meetings are taking place with all 4 capacity development country partners, whose details can be found in the project's SharePoint repository. In this context, Dr Nikas mentioned that WP6 has a very organised workflow with multiple meetings and everything proceeds smoothly. In this context, Dr Nikas and Dr Gardumi agreed to arrange a discussion on the country models's structure regarding WP2 on the 2nd RPM cycle. On behalf of the WI team, Ms. Lena Tholen (WI) mentioned that there are no major updates.</p> <p>In conclusion, Dr Nikas apologised for not leaving enough time for WP6 discussions and proposed that an Executive Board Meeting could take place in December (although it is not a usual practice) to further discuss WP6 matters.</p>	<p>Share the CDE progress presentation</p> <p>Determine the dates for the Sri Lanka and Ukraine workshops</p> <p>Discuss and organise a potential EBM for December</p>	<p>UPRC</p> <p>KTH</p> <p>NTUA</p>

2.3 Executive Board Meeting – 16 January 2024

2.3.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Tuesday, 16 January, 2024
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP6: Explaining
 - Task 6.1 – CDE progress so far (UPRC)
 - Task 6.2 – COP28 concluded, series of policy briefs stemming from PRM1 around springtime (NTUA, Bruegel)
 - Tasks 6.4-6.5 coordination (KTH, WI), including:
 - Drivers and barriers analysis (WI, sector study leads)
 - Progress regarding Ukraine, Sri Lanka, Ethiopia workshops (KTH, KEI, RUSL, AAiT)
 - WP5: Expanding
 - D5.1: Impact assessment of COVID-19 recovery COVID-19 analysis – January 2024 (E3M)
 - D5.2: Climate action social & distributional impacts: progress – February 2024 (BC3)
 - D5.4: Modelling out-of-ordinary extremes: progress – February 2024 (Imperial)
 - D5.6: Behaviour, social and disruptive innovation: progress – February 2024 (UNIGE / NTUA / UVa)
 - Task 5.6 – SDG mapping, biophysical limits review & SDG modelling: progress (CARTIF / UVa / NTUA)
 - WP4: Modelling
 - First modelling cycle: PRM1 Studies progress (Imperial & Study leads)
 - D4.5: National, regional, global mitigation pathways – November 2023 (Imperial)
 - D4.7: Sectoral and cross-sectoral analysis – December 2023 (WI)
 - D4.9: European sub-national deep dives – January 2024 (UNIGE)
 - WP3: Exchanging
 - D3.8: I2AM PARIS v2.0 – January 2024 (NTUA)
 - WP2: Listening
 - Core Working Groups –progress on regional events (Bruegel)
 - D2.4: Proceedings of Stakeholder interactions - January 2024 (Bruegel)

- WP1: Project Management
 - Midterm report & review meeting

2. Any other business

2.3.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	NTUA
2	Natasha Frilingou	NTUA
3	Konstantinos Koasidis	NTUA
4	Thomas Nikolakakis	NTUA
5	Ilkka Keppo	Aalto
6	Rasmus Magni Johanssen	AAU
7	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
8	Russell Horowitz	BC3
9	Claudia Rodés	BC3
10	Conall Heussaff	Bruegel
11	Adrian Lauer	Bruegel
12	Adrián Mateo Martínez	CARTIF
13	Noelia Ferreras Alonso	CARTIF
14	Glen Peters	CICERO
15	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
16	Eleftheria Zisarou	E3M
17	Panagiotis Fragkos	E3M
18	Anastasis Giannousakis	E3M
19	Eftychia Ntostoglou	KTH
20	Francesco Gardumi	KTH
21	Nikolaos Kleanthis	UPRC
22	Sophia Theodoropoulou	UPRC
23	Jaime Nieto	UVa
24	Dagmar Kigar	WI
25	Lena Tholen	WI
25	Wolfgang Obergassel	WI
26	Jyoti Maheshwari	IIMA
27	John Maitha Thoya	TUM
28	Salsabila Abdulhalim	TUM
29	Adam Hawkes	Imperial
30	Shivika Mittal	Imperial
31	Alaa Al Khourdajie	Imperial

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who

WP6	<p>The meeting started with Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) informing all partners that she will be moving from Imperial to CICERO, and for all WP4-related issues, the main contact point would now be Dr Alaa Al Khourdajie (Imperial). Next Mrs Sophia Theodoropoulou (UPRC) took the floor and presented the progress on CDE indicators & planned activities.</p> <p>Then, Dr Wolfgang Obergassel (WI) shared updates on Task 6.4, which synthesises mitigation drivers, barriers globally and in case study countries. A first draft of the four countries is already available, and the full report will be submitted in August 2024 (D6.6).</p> <p>Finally, Dr Francesco Gardumi (KTH) moved on to Task 6.5 regarding capacity development activities and case-study country models (D6.7). He mentioned the planned IAM COMPACT workshops in Ethiopia with our AAiT colleagues (23rd & 24th Jan), focused on electrification, and in Sri Lanka (31st Jan), focused on integrated assessment modelling using the CLEWs methodology. In Kenya, a modelling class has been set up as a partnership among TUM, Strathmore, and Meru universities, planned to start in February and last until July. In Ukraine, planning the workshop has been challenging, but our colleagues at KEI have been working on the model.</p> <p>Dr Mittal asked whether the case-study country models would be open, to which Dr Gardumi replied that all countries will use open-access tools.</p>	<p>Increase SoMe traffic & newsletter outreach</p> <p>Google Analytics data</p>	<p>URPC</p> <p>NTUA dev team</p>
WP5	<p>Dr Panagiotis Fragkos (E3M) informed the partners that D5.1, on the impact assessment of COVID-19 recovery, has been submitted for internal review, and is on track to be submitted by the end of the month. He moved on to Task 5.2, which will feature work from BC3, NTUA & E3M colleagues on climate action social & distributional impacts.</p> <p>Then, Dr Al Khourdajie shared updates on ongoing modelling work for disruptive and extreme events as part of Task 5.3, submitting D5.4 in early February.</p> <p>On Task 5.4 & Task 5.5, Ms. Natasha Frilingou (NTUA) will share the D5.6 chapter structure will all contributors, as the deliverable integrates two different tasks on Disruptive innovation & Behavioural change, as well as several PRM studies, to facilitate workflow. Then, Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) briefly informed the consortium about an upcoming publication led by the GCAM-USA team as part of D5.6, currently under review in npj.</p> <p>Finally, on Task 5.7, Dr Alexandros Nikas (NTUA) mentioned the ongoing contributions from Aalto, and UVA as well as a collaborative effort with NDC ASPECTS regarding modelling analysis of SDGs in IAMs.</p>	<p>Prioritise Task 5.3 scenarios comparison</p> <p>D5.6 chapter structure</p> <p>CCS study as part of D5.6</p>	<p>E3M</p> <p>NTUA</p> <p>CICERO</p>
WP4	<p>Dr Mittal started with the upcoming update of IAM COMPACT's Broad Scenario Logic, which aims to include new SSP pathways, provided they become available on time. Dr Jan Ivar Korsbakken (CICERO) added that CICERO will reach out to modelling teams for feedback regarding the usability of the Broad Scenario Logic and any recommendations regarding each update for the 2nd modelling cycle.</p> <p>She then focused on D4.5 regarding National, regional, and global mitigation pathways due in Feb 2024, to include national analysis for high-emitters (USA, China, India).</p>	<p>Broad Scenario Logic feedback</p> <p>D4.5 update (Feb 2024)</p> <p>D4.7 update (Feb 2024)</p>	<p>CICERO & modelling teams</p> <p>Imperial</p> <p>WI</p>

	<p>Then, she moved on to Task 4.4, where a first draft of D4.7 on sectoral and cross-sectoral analysis has been submitted and scheduled for update also in Feb 2024.</p> <p>Finally, D4.9 is already under review, focusing on European sub-national deep dives, and will be submitted by the end of the month as planned. She then gave the floor to Prof Rasmus Magni Johannsen (AAU) to briefly update the consortium on Study 2 which AAU is leading, as part of D4.9, a multi-model study which investigates renewable energy scenarios for Europe and Greece.</p>		
WP3	Ms. Frilingou briefly reported that the update of the I ² AM PARIS platform has been documented in D3.8, which is under review and is to be submitted by the end of the month.		
WP2	Mr Conall Heussaff (Bruegel) provided a brief update on the Policy Steering Groups & Core Working Groups conducted throughout last year, noting that feedback from interactions with China & USA stakeholders is still pending. All those interactions are being documented in D2.4 - Proceedings of Stakeholder Interaction, to be submitted by the end of the month.		
WP1	Finally, Dr Nikas reminded the partners that the reporting period is fast approaching, and NTUA will soon share guidelines with all the WP leads	Technical report template	NTUA

2.4 3rd General Assembly Meeting – 26, 27 February 2024

2.4.1 Agenda

Participants: All Partners

Day I: Progress on WPs 1-4 (MS Teams [link](#))

Monday, February 26, 2024			
09:45 – 10:00	Gathering, small talk, etc.		
10:00 – 10:30	I.1	WP1 – Project Management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordination - Management - Midterm review - guidance 	NTUA
10:30 – 11:30	I.2	WP2 – Listening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Progress and impressions from CWG exchanges - Finalising PRM Cycle #1 and preparing for Cycle #2 - Policy briefs 	Bruegel
11:30 – 12:15	I.3	WP3 – Exchanging <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open data management - Protocols for open science - Platform updates - Synergies & collaboration 	Imperial, BC3, NTUA
12:15 – 12:30	Short break		
12:30 – 14:15	I.4	WP4 – Modelling <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scenario logic & harmonisation (use & survey feedback) - National, global, regional mitigation pathways and Study 1 - Sectoral dynamics and cross-sectoral aspects and Study 4 - European sub-national deep dives and Study 2 	Imperial, CICERO, BC3, WI, NTUA
14:15 – 15:00	Discussion, Q&A		

Day II: Progress on WP5-6 & SAB meeting (MS Teams [link](#))

Tuesday, February 27, 2024			
09:45 – 10:00	Gathering, signing in, etc		
10:00 – 10:10	II.1	Wrap-up Day 1	NTUA
10:10 – 12:00	II.2	WP5 – Expanding <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COVID recovery analysis - Addressing distributional implications and gender inequality - Out-of-ordinary extremes and Study 3 - Disruptive innovation in models and Studies 5-6 - Behavioural change and social innovation and Study 7 - Truly sustainable decarbonisation pathways 	E3M, BC3, Imperial, NTUA, UVa, CARTIF
12:00 – 12:15	Short break		

12:15 – 13:15	II.3	WP6 – Explaining <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Communication, dissemination, and exploitation</i> - <i>KPIs monitoring</i> - <i>Drivers, barriers, and policy analysis</i> - <i>Capacity development (progress, next steps)</i> 	URPC, KTH, Bruegel, WI, AAIT, TUM, RUSL, KSE
13:15 – 14:15	II.4	Scientific Advisory Board <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Project planning/implementation & SAB feedback</i> 	SAB members, All partners
14:15 – 15:00	Discussion, Q&A		

2.4.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
Day I: Progress on WPs 1-4		
1	Alexandros Nikas	NTUA
2	Konstantinos Koasidis	NTUA
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	NTUA
4	Natasha Frilingou	NTUA
5	Thomas Nikolakakis	NTUA
6	Christina Tigka	NTUA
7	Ilkka Keppo	Aalto
8	Rasmus Magni Johanssen	AAU
9	Jakob Zinck Thellufsen	AAU
10	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
11	Russell Horowitz	BC3
12	Claudia Rodés	BC3
13	Jon Sampedro	BC3
14	Conall Heussaff	Bruegel
15	Adrián Lauer	Bruegel
16	Alma Kurtovic	Bruegel
17	Ugne Keliauskaite	Bruegel
18	Adrián Mateo Martínez	CARTIF
19	Noelia Ferreras Alonso	CARTIF
20	Glen Peters	CICERO
21	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
22	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
23	Eleftheria Zisarou	E3M
24	Panagiotis Fragkos	E3M
25	Anastasis Giannousakis	E3M
25	Maria-Iro Baka	E3M
26	Chamindie Senaratne	KTH
27	Francesco Gardumi	KTH
28	Nikolaos Kleanthis	UPRC
29	Sophia Theodoropoulou	UPRC
30	Vasilis Stavrakas	UPRC
31	Gonzalo Parrado Hernando	UVa
32	Wolfgang Obergassel	WI
33	John Maitha Thoya	TUM
34	Alaa Al Khourdajie	Imperial
Day II: Progress on WP5-6 & SAB meeting		
1	Alexandros Nikas	NTUA

2	Konstantinos Koasidis	NTUA
3	Anastasios Karamaneas	NTUA
4	Natasha Frilingou	NTUA
5	Thomas Nikolakakis	NTUA
6	Christina Tigka	NTUA
7	Ilkka Keppo	Aalto
8	Rasmus Magni Johanssen	AAU
9	Jakob Zinck Thellufsen	AAU
10	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
11	Russell Horowitz	BC3
12	Claudia Rodés	BC3
13	Jon Sampedro	BC3
14	Conall Heussaff	Bruegel
15	Adrián Lauer	Bruegel
16	Adrián Mateo Martínez	CARTIF
17	Noelia Ferreras Alonso	CARTIF
18	Glen Peters	CICERO
19	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
20	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
21	Eleftheria Zisarou	E3M
22	Panagiotis Fragkos	E3M
23	Anastasis Giannousakis	E3M
24	Maria-Iro Baka	E3M
25	Chamindie Senaratne	KTH
25	Francesco Gardumi	KTH
26	Nikolaos Kleanthis	UPRC
27	Sophia Theodoropoulou	UPRC
28	Vasilis Stavrakas	UPRC
29	Gonzalo Parrado Hernando	UVa
30	Wolfgang Obergassel	WI
31	John Maitha Thoya	TUM
32	Alaa Al Khourdajie	Imperial

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
Day I: Progress on WPs 1-4			
WP1	Dr Alexandros Nikas (NTUA) welcomed the partners and kicked off the meeting. He then proceeded with the WP1 presentation, starting from the recent progress made in terms of deliverables, and congratulating the consortium for managing to deliver all RP1 deliverables so far in time, presenting also the project's pipeline among WPs. He then showed next year's outlook, reminding the partners that two deliverables (D2.3 & D4.4) are due in July and three in August (D1.4, D6.6 & D6.7) so they should plan ahead in case they collide with their summer breaks. He then moved on to milestone progress, highlighting that MS5 & MS6 have been the most cross-collaborating outputs of the project so far. Following, he delved into specific aspects of Task 1.2, regarding the project's visual identity. In this context, he informed partners about a plan to release a white paper/policy brief documenting the 1 st PRM of IAM COMPACT	Share the first draft of the technical report with WP1 & WP3 Doodle poll for internal prep meeting for RP1	NTUA NTUA

	<p>and invited everyone to participate. Then, he moved on to aspects regarding the 1st PRM and explained what is required from all partners, WP leads, and admin/financial colleagues. He also encouraged partners to inform the NTUA administration of their future scientific output and also send the related datasets so they can be uploaded to the project's Zenodo repository. Next, he briefed the consortium on the elements of Part A that they have to update on SyGMA, focusing on financial statements and the "researchers involved" tab. In the same context, he also provided guidance for Elements of Part B that need to be updated, stressing the online review meeting taking place on the 29th of May. Moreover, Dr Nikas presented the feedback that the SAB provided to the consortium in the previous SAB session regarding project management and project outputs as well. Finally, WP1 ended by presenting the timeline of the 2nd RPM, along with anticipated challenges</p>		
WP2	<p>Next, Ms. Ugne Keliauskaite (Bruegel) took the floor and presented the objectives of WP2, and its work related to policy-relevant themes. She then proceeded to a summary of outputs to date, as well as the next steps regarding the PRM. These include summarising the outputs from the modelling studies of the 1st cycle, getting feedback from Policy Steering Groups on scenario design and desirable outcomes, and then possibly proceeding on re-runs and their dissemination through policy briefs, which will mark the finalisation of the 1st PRM.</p> <p>Next, she delved into a more detailed presentation of outputs on four thematic areas: optimal transition, industry and innovation, global effects and behavioural change. For these thematic areas, the stakeholders involved were presented as well as the focus of each Policy Steering Group. Moreover, the research studies for the 1st PRM were briefly presented for each thematic area and Core Working Group, focusing on the participating stakeholders and the takeaways of each Group meeting.</p> <p>Following this, Ms. Keliauskaite proceeded to the presentation of the workshops of 7 non-European partners, which were separated into major emitters (USA, China and India) and non-high-income countries (the 4 case study countries: Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka and Ukraine). After briefing the consortium on the outcomes of its workshop, she highlighted that a large pool of stakeholders, good timing and clarity in communication, as well as online tools such as Miro ensured a successful and useful outcome. Finally, she overviewed the WP next steps focusing on the ongoing modelling and how the project should move on into the 2nd PRM cycle.</p> <p>In this context, a long discussion took place involving researchers from many project partners, such as Dr Shivika Mittal (CICERO), Dr Alaa Al Khourdajie (Imperial), Dr Francesco Gardumi (KTH), Dr Dirk-Jan van de Ven (BC3), Prof Ilkka Keppo (Aalto), Mr Adrian Lauer (Bruegel), Ms. Natasha Frilingou (NTUA) and Dr Nikas. This discussion had three main pillars. The main point raised was the 2nd PRM cycle, for which modelling issues were discussed such as the</p>	<p>Meeting for 2nd PRM</p> <p>Modelling study leads to providing feedback on the 1st modelling cycle.</p>	<p>Bruegel</p> <p>All modelling teams</p>

	<p>requirement for totally new model runs, harmonisation aspects as well as technology aspects (e.g., the inclusion of heat pumps). Apart from modelling issues, management issues were also discussed, with Dr Nikas ensuring that NTUA administration will use all available feedback to make everything more manageable and well-coordinated for the 2nd PRM cycle. The second subject of this long discussion was how IPCC's AR6 and AR7 have proceeded in various modelling aspects and how the project should update SSP scenarios which has just been released. Lastly, the number of studies for the 2nd PRM cycle was discussed with all partners agreeing that this cycle should have fewer studies than the first one.</p>		
WP3	<p>The session for WP3 started with Ms. Frilingou taking the floor and demonstrating the issues that will be discussed in a Task-based format. Then Dr Mittal took the floor to present the progress achieved in Task 3.1, regarding data management. She briefed the consortium on the Task's activities and objectives and the progress made so far, focusing on the ARGOS platform. Then, she presented the models used for each case study country and the relevant open-access licenses.</p> <p>Moreover, Prof Keppo presented the work done in Task 3.2, focusing on D3.5, which studies model interlinkages and integration and is due in April 2025. In his presentation, he mentioned that D3.5 will apply the methodologies defined in D3.4 to confirm the appropriate level of integration, exploit the consortium's modelling diversity and contribute to interpreting model outcomes.</p> <p>Moving to Task 3.3, Ms. Clàudia Rodés (BC3) briefed the partners on protocols for open science, demonstrating a schematic illustration of the concept and the benefits of using open protocols. Next, she showcased the IAM COMPACT Open Science Protocol, mentioning its goal as well as how consortium partners can contribute to this. She focused on the harmonisation process as well as the open management of project outcomes. She also presented the model documentation process that can be accessed in the I²AM PARIS platform, stressing the need to connect it with other documentation platforms. In this context, she also presented a heatmap for all project models which demonstrates whether each model allows model comparison in the platform. Next, she presented the model interconnections that take place in the project's studies. Additionally, she briefed the consortium on raw output storage, referring to a paper published by Sampedro et al. in 2024. Furthermore, she presented the processes that must be applied to validate and visualise outputs in order that all project models homogenise the visualisation of their results, mentioning that the project provides the necessary tools via the I²AM PARIS platform. Then, Ms. Rodés briefed the partners on the open-source tools (such as Zenodo and GitHub) that can be used to openly share the project's results. Finally, she concluded by presenting the next steps for Task 3.3, focusing on D3.7. Following this, Dr Jan Ivar Korsbakken (CICERO), Dr Mittal, Ms. Frilingou and Dr Gardumi had a discussion on the</p>	<p>Meeting for Diagnostics</p> <p>Meeting for model integration</p>	<p>NTUA, all modelling teams</p> <p>NTUA, all modelling teams</p>

	<p>licensing and specifically the type of licenses needed for the project’s training material, with Dr Gardumi suggesting the CC BY 4.0 is sufficient since the material is in Microsoft Office files.</p> <p>Next, Ms. Frilingou took the floor, presenting Task 3.4, focusing on D3.8 regarding the second version of the I²AM PARIS platform, which will include validation processes and will also be used for other projects as well (such as DIAMOND and TRANSCIENCE) ensuring that the platform will be functional for several years after the end of the IAM COMPACT project. In this context, she briefed the partners on the planned activities to improve the platform and the targets that the consortium has set (e.g., creating 10 new workspaces).</p> <p>The next task discussed was Task 3.6, with Dr Korsbakken starting his presentation with the validation and vetting checks that model run should undergo, mentioning that the platform will accommodate relevant tools. In this context, Dr Mittal, Dr Korsbakken, Dr Al Khourdajie and Prof Keppo had a discussion on vetting checks with Dr Mittal proposing that the consortium can learn from IPCC’s AR6 processes and Prof Keppo mentioning feasibility and historical data harmonisation issues. Next, Dr Korsbakken continued his presentation briefing the consortium on the diagnostics processes, their main objective as well as the actions that will take place in the project’s context. He also presented the proposed diagnostic scenarios and some discussion points. In this context, Dr Mittal, Dr Korsbakken and Prof Keppo discussed model development and model behaviour issues and how diagnostics can help improve the models.</p> <p>Lastly, Ms. Frilingou took the floor and briefed the partners on the project’s progress and planning on synergies, focusing on the project’s scientific outreach and capacity development activities so far.</p>		
WP4	<p>Dr Al Khourdajie took the floor, presenting briefly the WP4 contents.</p> <p>The first presentation by Dr Korsbakken overviewed Deliverables 4.3 and 4.4 and then proceeded to the takeaways of the survey that was conducted in the context of D4.3 from CICERO the month before. Then, Dr Korsbakken and Dr van de Ven discussed technological parameters, stressing the issue that these cannot be easily harmonised since every model represents them quite differently. Next, Dr Gardumi suggested that KTH and CICERO organise a bilateral meeting for land-use issues. In this context, Dr Mittal added some comments regarding the modelling of agricultural mechanisms and how IAMs can be used in this direction. In the same context, Mr Gonzalo Parrado Hernando (UVA) mentioned that WILIAM needs more disaggregated data for its land-use module.</p> <p>Next, Dr van de Ven took the floor for Task 4.3 and presented the three sub-studies included in D4.5. The first one, starting with the research questions that this study aims to answer, as well as some details for this study (such as the participating models). Furthermore, he briefed the attendees on the model protocol applied, presenting each scenario and</p>	<p>Meeting for scenario results</p> <p>Meeting for the coordination of the update of D4.2</p> <p>Meeting for land-use issues</p>	<p>CICERO</p> <p>CARTIF</p> <p>KTH, CICERO</p>

its targets. Next, he demonstrated a set of results figures, including CO₂ emissions by sector, final energy consumption by fuel and sector and renewables share on final energy usage. He ended his presentation by mentioning the study's conclusions. In this context, Dr Mittal and Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) discussed the inclusion of DAC technologies in models and Dr van de Ven replied that GCAM consider negative emissions technologies.

Following this, Dr Georg Holtz (WI) proceeded to present Task 4.4, which included four sub-studies. The first one examines the European Steel Industry, focusing on investigating how trade restrictions and decarbonisation pathways affect the European steel sector. He also demonstrated the approach of this study, the scenarios studied as well and some results on steel production from different models. Next, he presented some conclusions and insights from this study as well as areas for future work for the 2nd PRM cycle.

Next, Mr Gonzalo Parrado Hernando (Uva) took the floor to present the second study on re-shoring critical industries to the EU. He briefed the consortium on the relevant EU policy acts as well as the research question examined in this study and demonstrated the interaction between participating models GCAM and WILIAM as well as the mineral intensities for new plants and the recycling rates for each mineral. Lastly, he presented results of modelling runs and conclusions from this study.

Following this, Mr Nikos Kleanthis (UPRC) presented the third study on decarbonisation pathways of the Greek power sector, starting with the background and main research question. Additionally, he presented the models used for the study and the connection between them as well as the scenario design. Lastly, he presented some core results and some useful insights.

He also presented a second study by UPRC, focusing on small-scale PVs, for which he once again presented the main research question, and the model used (ATOM) as well as the model parameters and the model's calibration. Finally, he presented the scenario design, some core results and some insightful conclusions.

Next, Ms. Frilingou took the floor and presented the progress of Task 4.5, showcasing the aims and objectives of the relevant deliverable. The session continued with Prof Rasmus Magni Johannsen (AAU) presenting Study 2 on energy security, starting with the aims of the study. Then, he mentioned the models used and the scenarios simulated, including European and Greek scenarios. He also presented the Shannon diversity index as well as results on energy consumption and generation. The study also assessed three types of electrical loads, examining the demand and supply capacities for different scenarios. A set of results regarding the flexibility of the system, the environmental effects as well as costs and prices were also explained. Lastly, he briefed the partners on some core conclusions of the study. In this context, Dr Mittal and Prof Johannsen discussed the role of hydrogen storage on flexibility with Prof Johannsen

	<p>mentioning that hydrogen is mainly used for the production of e-fuels and not for electricity generation.</p> <p>The last presentation was conducted by Mr Adrián Mateo (CARTIF) and focused on the outputs of D4.1, focusing on the representation of the policy categorisation method, policy representation in IAMC models and policy question categories. Next, he presented the coordination with other WPs for D4.2 as well as the next steps required.</p> <p>In this context, Ms. Frilingou pointed out that D4.1 was one of the first deliverables of the First Modelling Cycle, completed before the full set of policy questions from the PRM were available. She then asked partners how D4.2 could prove more useful to the next modelling cycle, in terms of the framework and policies included. Mr Adrian replied that indeed D4.1 felt isolated from the modelling work, and it would be beneficial for everyone if more connections were explored. Dr Van de Ven suggested that D4.2 could take stock for the Current Policies and NDCs included in the scenario framework of the first modelling cycle in global models, while Dr Mittal pointed out that apart from the global policies, CARTIF could also include sectoral and national policies that were included in the modelling runs of e.g., GCAM-USA, and D4.5 could be a their starting point of reference.</p>		
Wrap-up Day 1	Finally, Ms. Frilingou recapped the meetings that were proposed during the call to coordinate work among WPs and thanked the partners for their presentations and their time.	-	-
Day II: Progress on WP5-6 & SAB meeting			
WP5	<p>The meeting started with Dr Panagiotis Fragkos (E3M) providing an overview of WP5, its overreaching goals and encompassing studies as well as the planning for the following deliverables and milestones. Next, he briefed the consortium on the structure of the WP5 session for the EBM. Ms. Eleftheria Zisarou (E3M) then discussed the results of Task 5.1, starting from the classification of announced recovery packages, and moving on to the scenarios simulated as well as the use of a series of national and global modelling tools, to analyse the short- and long-term emissions, of energy system, technology, and macroeconomic implications of these packages. She also presented a set of results for the scenarios modelled that focused on selected major emitters, and employment impacts of the electricity sector (bottom-up and top-down ones).</p> <p>Next Mr Kleantithis took the floor and presented the work on the study focusing on the Greek RRF components and actions. He briefed the consortium on each component, mentioning the types of measures and the technologies used. He then focused on the models used as well as the scenarios modelled and showcased a set of core results and some fundamental insights of the study.</p> <p>Next, Dr Xaquín García-Muros (BC3) took the floor to present the progress made on D5.2. He started by presenting the 3 pillars of the deliverable: the socioeconomic impacts of the Energy Taxation Directive (ETD), energy poverty & just transformation in Greece as well as MEDUSA, a tool for</p>		

distributional analysis with IAM inputs. Regarding the first pillar, he briefed the consortium on the new ETD proposal, describing some scenarios as well. He also presented the current effective energy tax rates in each EU member state. Additionally, he demonstrated some figures regarding the distributional impacts of the various ETD scenarios and mentioned some important conclusions of this work.

Following, Dr Fragkos continued the presentation informing the consortium of the objectives of the study on energy poverty and just transformation in Greece. Then, he presented the scenario design and some figures on socioeconomic and distributional effects. His presentation also included results on decarbonisation effects on energy poverty as well as some key insights.

Dr García-Muros once again took the floor to present the MEDUSA tool, starting by describing the tool, which is an R package soft-linked with a household budget survey. Next, he presented some core functions of this tool as well as its website, mentioned that BC3 aims to expand the tool to use annual data, and finally its capacity to be soft-linked with GCAM.

Next, the session moved to D5.4, with Dr Al Khourdajie taking the floor, and presenting its objectives, a set of indicative questions as well as a series of extreme events and tipping points that can be examined. He then provided some illustrative examples of the role of IAMs in this analysis, as well as the scenario framework which comprises four narratives regarding the level of transformational response and the level of resilience to socioeconomic impacts. Moreover, he mentioned that a set of expert interviews took place in which a variety of topics were discussed, such as defining extremes and geopolitical factors.

Following this, Ms. Zisarou continued the session by presenting Study 3, which examines geopolitics and energy transition. After describing the aim of the study, she mentioned the disruptive scenarios examined and how they can be placed in the scenario framework Dr Khourdajie presented before. Following this, she demonstrated a set of figures on impacts regarding CO₂ emissions, primary energy and electricity generation. Lastly, she summarised some key points.

Then, Ms. Frilingou took the floor to present the work done on D5.6, starting with a study from UNIGE on probabilistic assessment of energy technologies diffusion. Next, she focused on a study regarding the minimization of the use of CDR while still achieving net-zero emissions, and demonstrated some results from the GCAM model, accompanied by a set of figures and a couple of useful insights. Afterwards, Dr Khourdajie moved to present a study examining the impact of investors' expectations and climate risk assessment on mitigation scenarios, starting by describing the IAM-CFR framework, which links climate mitigation pathways with the financial system. He then presented the scenarios modelled as well as the workflow applied to map interest rates to original scenarios. Additionally, he demonstrated a set of results figures on

	<p>carbon budget, temperature change and CO₂ net zero year. Remaining on D5.6, but moving to Study 7, Mr Parrado Hernando presented the objectives of this study as well as some relevant indicative questions from the PRM. In addition, he briefed the consortium on the literature review on behavioural change as well as on the role of IAMs in this field. He described the scenario framework and how each model is used in the context of this study and showcased a set of results for the transport and buildings sectors as well as the impacts of diets. He concluded his presentation by summarising some key points.</p> <p>After, Mr Mateo took the floor to present the progress made on Task 5.6, commencing with the goals of the task, through a schematic illustration of the methodology and its produced outputs. He also presented a couple of figures on modelling results regarding SDG synergies. Afterwards, he presented a set of biodiversity metrics that are important to examine synergies and reinforce ecosystems. He then described a relevant submodule of materials in WILIAM 1.2 BETA, which is used to study the extraction flow of materials, and closed with potential improvements of Study 7, including the representation of freight transport in WILIAM.</p>		
WP6	<p>After a short break, the session for WP6 started with Dr Gardumi taking the floor, describing the WP's Tasks, deliverables and milestones. He then presented some deviations from the initial planning mainly due to the war in Ukraine which may lead to some delays. He then briefed the consortium on the next steps as well as the non-scientific outreach of the project.</p> <p>Next, Mr Carsten Elsner (WI) presented the progress made on Task 6.4, starting with the research approach followed and the current status of the task. Then, he described the Ukrainian case study, focusing on the status of work and the characteristics of the country. He did the same for the other three case study counties, i.e., Ethiopia, Kenya and Sri Lanka. Afterwards, Dr Gardumi continued the session with Task 6.5, demonstrating the approach followed via a Miro Board illustration. Then, he presented some key aspects of this task as well as the status of each case study country. For each country, he presented the focal point of the study, the tools used, the workshops hosted so far as well as the status of the work done. For Ethiopia, he also demonstrated an illustrative figure of the linkages among resources, technologies and end-use demands. Then, he presented the training materials that were prepared for Milestone 6 and briefed the consortium on the links with other WPs via a schematic illustration. Lastly, he prepared a short review of what the SAB had suggested and how the project can move towards this direction regarding WP6 and co-creation.</p> <p>Following, Dr Mittal and Dr Gardumi had a short discussion on preparing a set of best practices drawing from the project's experience on workshops etc.</p> <p>Afterwards, Ms. Sophia Theodoropoulou (UPRC) proceeded with Task 6.1, and demonstrated the timeline of the task's deliverables regarding the CDE plan of the project. Next, she presented the project's progress on its CDE indicators,</p>		

generally showing good performance so far, except the return and bounce rate of visitors on the I²AM PARIS platform website, and a low performance on the return of visitors on the project's website. She shared some figures on the number of visitors per country, focusing on some African countries. Then, she presented the number of visitors from each country focusing on the case study countries, as well as the performance of the project's scientific outreach which is well on track. Regarding non-scientific outreach, the performance is slightly lower but will be improved through the upcoming policy briefs documenting the 1st PRM cycle. She also demonstrated a set of metrics for the project's social media accounts and posts, presented the CDE monitoring tool, allowing all partners to see the progress of the CDE activities and update it if need be.

Next, Dr Nikas and Ms. Theodoropoulou had a discussion on the project's CDE performance so far. In this context, she mentioned that the overall performance is good, but she mentioned that specifically there are some performance issues regarding the expected outcomes. In particular, she stressed the need to increase the number of policy briefs and the number of stakeholders in the stakeholder database. They also had a short discussion on measuring the citations of the project's papers. In this context, Dr Mittal added that citations are a long-term metric that is not so helpful and suggested focusing on how many people read the papers etc. Moreover, Ms. Frilingou mentioned the report on the scientific outreach so far which has all the necessary data, while Dr Nikas focused on the fact for certain publications acknowledging the project, good coordination is needed since the timing is not the favourable *vis-à-vis* the project's timeline, e.g., the IPCC cities special report is expected in 2026 and the GEO7 report is in 2026. Nevertheless, he concluded that this is an impact, so it is not crucial to make it.

Dr Nikas and Ms. Theodoropoulou had a brief discussion on the project's final conference and where it can take place. In another context, Dr Nikas stressed the importance of reaching the project goals in all aspects and also trying to overperform in as many as possible.

Next, Dr Gardumi, Mr. Lauer, Dr Nikas and Ms. Frilingou discussed that the project will produce numerous briefs so this target will be met by the end of the project's lifetime.

Moreover, Ms. Frilingou and Dr Gardumi discussed creating an infographic for each case study country to make information more digestible for people.

In addition, Dr Mittal and Mr. Lauer had a discussion on formulating the policy briefs necessary for the project's outreach, discussing issues such as timing as well.

Next, Dr Nikas briefed the partners on a couple of loose ends for some deliverables. In this context, Dr Gardumi, Dr Nikas and Ms. Frilingou discussed that some uploaded materials do not have the necessary license information printed and that they need to be revised.

Finally, Dr Nikas thanked everybody for attending the meeting.

SAB	Partners discussed key points stemming from previous SAB feedback, which revolved around the project's modelling validation procedures, behavioural change aspects and how they are included in our modelling studies, as well as the involvement of non-EU partners and their ownership of outputs.		
Q&A, Feedback	N/A		

2.5 Executive Board Meeting – 28 March 2023

2.5.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Tuesday, 28 March, 2022
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Project Management
 - Partners not yet paid (actions pending!)
 - Next (hybrid) project GA meeting in September?
 - WP2: Listening
 - D2.2: Scoping policy relevant Research Questions (Bruegel) – UP
 - WP3: Exchanging
 - Model interlinkages meeting (March 20-23, 2023, TBC)
 - D3.4: Model interlinkages and integration (Aalto) – April 2023
 - MS4: Plan on collaboration and synergies (NTUA) – April 2023
 - WP4: Modelling
 - D4.1: From policy needs to scenario frameworks (CARTIF) – March 2023
 - Energy crisis (NTUA, several partners) – progress
 - EC's request on EU climate target for 2040 – end of April 2023
 - D4.3: Broad scenario logic (CICERO) – May 2023
 - WP5: Expanding
 - WP5 kick-off meeting aftermath, next steps (March 23, 2023)
 - WP6: Explaining
 - Task 6.4 & 6.5 coordination (KTH, WI)
 - Kenya workshop back-to-back with African Summit (Aug-Sep)?
2. Pending requests (outstanding pre-financing transfers) – NTUA
3. Next meetings (GA/consortium meeting, Kenya workshop, etc.) – All partners
4. Any other business

2.5.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Alexandros Nikas	NTUA
2	Anastasios Karamaneas	NTUA
3	Ilkka Keppo	Aalto
4	Jakob Zinck Thellufsen	AAU
5	Rasmus Magni Johannsen	AAU
6	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
7	Conall Heussaff	Bruegel
8	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
9	Glen Peters	CICERO
10	Panagiotis Fragkos	E3M
11	Eleftheria Zisarou	E3M
12	Francesco Gardumi	KTH
13	Lorenzo Rinaldi	POLIMI
14	Vassilis Stavrakas	UPRC
15	Nikolaos Kleanthis	UPRC
16	Jaime Nieto	UVa
17	Georg Holtz	WI
18	Zongfei Wang	WI
19	Saritha Vishwanathan	IIMA
20	Jyoti Maheswari	IIMA
21	Yu Wang	THU
22	Ioannis Tsipouridis	TUM
23	Jan-Philipp Sasse	UNIGE
24	Ajay Gambhir	Imperial
25	Shivika Mittal	Imperial

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	Dr Alexandros Nikas (NTUA) commenced the meeting by greeting the consortium. The first issue he posed was the fact that some partners have still not signed the Consortium Agreement, hence some payments may be missing.	CA signing	Remaining partners
	The next issue discussed was the date and location of the next General Assembly (GA) meeting. The main idea is that it takes place in a hybrid form in Kenya at the end of August or the beginning of September. In this context, Prof Ioannis Tsipouridis (TUM) mentioned that they have already done some planning since a capacity-building workshop will take place in TUM at the end of August in the scope of WP6. He also stated that they intend to make the workshop as inclusive as possible. Next, Dr Francesco Gardumi (KTH) took the floor informing the partners that TUM and KTH are working on the workshop's agenda. It will take place in the last week of August in Mombasa, Kenya and it will be a few days' workshop. Partners from POLIMI as well as the case study countries will participate. Moreover, Prof Tsipouridis stressed that the consortium should strive for stakeholder engagement even before the workshop. In this context, Dr Nikas proposed that, if the GA is somehow linked to the	Finalise the agenda of the capacity-building workshop Discussion on the organisation of the GA in Mombasa	TUM, KTH NTUA, TUM

	<p>workshop, it would be more realistic to organise the GA parallelly to the climate summit (taking place in Nairobi at the beginning of September) to maximise participation in the GA. Then, he suggested that a meeting takes place in the next few weeks to discuss this issue. Prof Tsipouridis mentioned that the workshop will begin on Monday the 28th of August (Dr Gardumi mentioned that this date is locked) and Dr Nikas suggested that it would be convenient if the GA took place on Thursday/Friday depending on the workshop's agenda. Moreover, Dr Nikas and Prof Ilkka Keppo (Aalto) had a short discussion on how the GA and the workshop can be intertwined, with Dr Nikas suggesting that if few partners participate in the workshop Kenya may not be the best idea for the GA. Nevertheless, Prof Tsipouridis stressed that TUM is capable of hosting the GA back-to-back with the workshop. The discussion closed with Prof Jakob Zinck Thellufsen (AAU) proposing that, if the GA does not take place in Kenya, it should not take place back-to-back with the workshop since many partners would want to participate in the climate summit in Nairobi.</p>		
WP2	<p>Next, Mr Conall Heussaff (Bruegel) took the floor and briefed the consortium on the progress of WP2. First, he mentioned that stakeholder meetings led to a slight delay regarding the results of the Policy Steering processes. Then, he mentioned that non-EU partners have been very responsive so far with partners from TUM and KEI already communicating with stakeholders. He also proposed that a meeting is organised in a couple of weeks to further organises this process. In this context, Dr Nikas proposed that the consortium should not wait for all meetings to further proceed since this may jeopardise the whole mechanism. Next, Dr Gardumi and Mr Heussaff had a brief discussion on the feedback from RUSL and AAiT partners, who have also contacted stakeholders but have not received any feedback yet. They also discussed Bruegel's participation in the Kenyan workshop. Lastly, Dr Nikas briefed the partners on the deliverables' timeline.</p>	Set up a meeting for WP2 stakeholder engagement	NTUA, Bruegel
WP3	<p>Prof Keppo took the floor and informed the partners that a meeting for WP3 will take place on the 3rd of April. He also pinpointed the overlap between Task 4.1 and Task 3.2 since both Tasks focus on models, but with different scopes, mentioning that there is a deadline for input by Friday the 31st of March. Prof Keppo also stated that research questions affect models and how they will be used in the project's context. Next, Dr Nikas mentioned that in the second iteration, the consortium may have the opportunity to better time all processes. He also stressed that typologies should be set and that models should be mapped according to these typologies in order to examine which models are more relevant and how scenarios can be set, a process which can also help the Policy Response Mechanism. In this context, Prof Keppo stressed that the consortium should focus on the typologies and spend more time on them to further enhance the second modelling cycle. Nevertheless, the timing problem is also evident in the second cycle since the deliverable for the research questions is close to the discussed deliverable of the second cycle. Lastly, Dr Shivika Mittal (Imperial) and</p>	Set model typologies	All modelling partners, Aalto
		Prepare MS4	NTUA

	<p>Dr Nikas briefly discussed the creation of a relevant workspace in the I²AM PARIS platform.</p> <p>The previous thorough discussion also covered all the relevant matters regarding D3.4.</p> <p>Dr Nikas closed the discussion on WP3 by mentioning that Milestone 4 (scheduled for April) is a simple task which should focus on sister projects and that will resemble a strategy.</p>		
WP4	<p>Afterwards, Dr Ajay Gambhir (Imperial) took the floor and informed the consortium that WP4 deliverables are under progress with the two first being delivered by the end of March and May respectively. Dr Nikas mentioned that D4.1 has received good reviews and is already submitted meeting most of the expected outcomes. He also stressed the importance of tracking changes and not deleting comments during the internal review process to simplify the reviewer's work.</p>		
	<p>Moreover, Dr Gambhir stressed that the consortium has to complete an analysis of the EU's 2040 target by the end of April</p>	Prepare the EU 2040 target analysis	All modelling partners
	<p>Next, Dr Nikas, Dr Mittal and Dr Gambhir had a brief discussion regarding the energy crisis study. They mentioned that a brief will be available in April and that the study will be accompanied by an analysis of the PARIS REINFORCE project that is still active. In this context, Dr Nikas informed the partners that he and Dr Mittal will participate in an event on diagnostics organised by the EC to represent PARIS REINFORCE and IAM COMPACT projects.</p>	Finalise the energy crisis study and prepare a relevant brief	NTUA, all modelling partners
	<p>The last issue discussed regarding WP4 was D4.3 on the broad scenario logic. Dr Jan Ivar Korsbakken (CICERO) informed the consortium that the deliverable is progressing as planned, as partners have already provided their input. He mentioned that this deliverable aims to set the scenario logic, focusing on assumptions and data that will be used without diving into specific narrow scenarios. Dr Mittal proposed that the consortium should work on calibration and harmonisation for a week before delivering D4.3 and Dr Korsbakken proposed that a first draft will be available by the start of May and in this stage, reviewers can make recommendations on calibration and harmonisation and if everything is OK the draft can be finalised.</p>	Prepare a first draft of D4.3	CICERO
WP5	<p>Next, Dr Panagiotis Fragkos (E3M) took the floor and informed the partners that the WP's kick-off meeting took place this month and that tasks are already in progress. Specifically, regarding Task 5.1, he mentioned that the collection of data from the Green Recovery Packages of EU countries has already started, and that the Consortium intends to proceed to the data collection for non-EU countries as well. Lastly, he stressed that mapping policy questions with WP5 tasks is important to examine if they can reply to these questions.</p>	Green Recovery Packages data collection	E3M, all partners
WP6	<p>Dr Gardumi immediately proceeded to the joint meeting for Tasks 6.4 and 6.5 since the workshop and possible GA hosting were already thoroughly discussed during the session on WP1. He proposed that a joint meeting is organised every two months. He also stated that the research framework</p>	Organise the next joint meeting for Tasks 6.4 and 6.5	KTH

	from WP4 works properly for WP6. Lastly, he suggested that a timeline for deliverables of Tasks 6.4 and 6.5 must be set with an ending date on M24.		
	The meeting concluded with Dr Vasilis Stavrakas (UPRC) informing the consortium that CDE activities are in progress and that the second newsletter is already being prepared.	Finalise the second newsletter	UPRC, NTUA
Any other business	No other business was discussed since all issues were covered during the relevant WPs sessions.	-	-

2.6 Executive Board Meeting – 23 April 2024

2.6.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Tuesday, 23 April, 2024
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Project Management
 - Feedback on the interim report
 - Review meeting rehearsal date (May 2024)
 - Finding hosts for next physical GA meeting (October 2024)
 - WP6: Explaining
 - Task 6.1 – CDE progress tracking (UPRC)
 - Task 6.4 – Drivers, barriers, and policy analysis progress (WI)
 - D6.6 (Aug 2024)
 - Task 6.5 – Progress on case study country workshops & models (KTH, KEI, TUM, RUSL, AAiT)
 - D6.7 (Aug 2024)
 - EGU aftermath (BC3, Imperial, NTUA)
 - WP5: Expanding
 - Task 5.6 – SDG mapping, biophysical limits review & SDG modelling: progress (CARTIF, UVa, NTUA, Aalto, BC3)
 - D5.8 (May 2024)
 - Task 5.7 – A novel approach to ‘expanded multi-model assessment’ (E3M)
 - Gathering all modelling outputs from RP1 (NTUA)
 - Potential follow-up modelling in response to PRM feedback.
 - WP4: Modelling
 - Task 4.3 – Broad scenario logic update (CICERO)
 - Potential follow-up modelling in response to PRM feedback.
 - WP3: Exchanging
 - Task 3.6 – Scenario validation and diagnostics (CICERO)
 - WP2: Listening
 - Non-EU stakeholder engagement plan (Bruegel, Non-EU partners)
2. Any other business

2.6.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Natasha Frilingou	NTUA
2	Anastasios Karamaneas	NTUA
3	Ilkka Keppo	Aalto
4	Rasmus Magni Johanssen	AAU
5	Jakob Zinck Thellufsen	AAU
6	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
7	Russell Horowitz	BC3
8	Claudia Rodés	BC3
9	Jon Sampedro	BC3
10	Conall Heussaff	Bruegel
11	Adrián Lauer	Bruegel
12	Adrián Mateo Martínez	CARTIF
13	Noelia Ferreras Alonso	CARTIF
14	Glen Peters	CICERO
15	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
16	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
17	Eleftheria Zisarou	E3M
18	Panagiotis Fragkos	E3M
19	Anastasis Giannousakis	E3M
20	Maria-Iro Baka	E3M
21	Chamindie Senaratne	KTH
22	Francesco Gardumi	KTH
23	Nikolaos Kleanthis	UPRC
24	Sophia Theodoropoulou	UPRC
25	Vasilis Stavrakas	UPRC
25	Gonzalo Parrado Hernando	UVa
26	Wolfgang Obergassel	WI
27	Saritha Sudharmma Vishwanathan	IIMA
28	Jyoti Maheshwari	IIMA
29	Yu Wang	THU
30	Solomon Teferi	AAiT
31	John Maitha Thoya	TUM
32	Ioannis Tsipouridis	TUM
33	Alaa Al Khourdajie	Imperial

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	<p>The meeting started with Ms. Natasha Frilingou (NTUA) greeting all the partners and asking them if they needed any help or instructions regarding the technical reporting of the project. In this context, Dr Shivika Mittal (CICERO) made a question regarding the Policy Response Mechanism (PRM) and the technical reporting with Ms. Frilingou replying that the technical report should outline the areas that each task covers.</p> <p>Next, Ms. Frilingou and Mr Adrián Lauer (Bruegel) had a short discussion on how the technical report parts that its partner delivers will be reviewed, with Ms. Frilingou stating that small changes will take place from the NTUA administration team.</p>	Send technical report parts to NTUA	All partners, NTUA

	<p>Afterwards, Ms. Frilingou and Dr Alaa Al Khourdajie (Imperial) discussed a shared file indicating all the data is missing and required for the technical reporting.</p> <p>Moreover, Ms. Frilingou mentioned that RUSL has not yet signed the Consortium Agreement (due to internal issues) which can create some issues for the financial reporting and Dr Francesco Gardumi (KTH) proposed that KTH can help if help is needed.</p> <p>Next, Ms. Frilingou and Prof Saritha Sudharma Vishwanathan (IIMA) discussed IIMA's project regarding technical reporting with Dr Mittal mentioning that IIMA's progress is on time.</p> <p>Lastly, Prof Yu Wang (THU) informed Ms. Frilingou that she will send the following day an e-mail with her questions.</p>		
WP2	<p>Moving to WP2, Mr. Conall Heussaff (Bruegel) briefed the partners on the progress of this Work Package and stated that the consortium should inform the stakeholders of the progress of the 1st modelling cycle. He also presented the following process, as well as the process for the non-EU countries. He also suggested that a discussion with modelling teams take place to determine the next steps of the process, with Dr Mittal proposing that a common language between all models is adopted for Task 4.3 for the 2nd cycle. In this context, she also mentioned that there are two ways to connect global and national models with Prof Ilkka Keppo (Aalto) replying that connecting global and national studies can demonstrate various constraints, proposing that it could be better to avoid combining everything in the process of the PRM. In this context, Ms. Frilingou proposed to arrange a separate meeting to discuss these complicated matters, with Dr Gardumi mentioning that connecting studies is more meaningful for major emitters. Nevertheless, he also mentioned that there are issues for the case study countries (e.g. a probable inclusion of Ukraine in the EU), repeating the need for a separate meeting. Moreover, Prof Sudharma Vishwanathan mentioned the need to clarify if the consortium aims to soft-link models or inter-compare them, and the need for efficiency in national models as well. In this context, Mr Heussaff stated that Bruegel has no preference on which method will be followed with Dr Mittal and Prof Keppo engaging in a discussion regarding the timeline of the 2nd PRM.</p>	<p>Arrange a meeting for the next modelling steps</p>	<p>NTUA, all modelling partners</p>
WP3	<p>Next, Dr Jan Ivar Korsbakken (CICERO) took the floor informing the partners on the progress of Task 3.6. He mentioned that CICERO is running validation checks and that they will send to all modelling partners relevant requests. In the same context, he stated that the validation code is executable locally but not online yet. Next, he and Dr Mittal proceeded to a brief presentation of the vetting checks progress. Afterwards, Dr Korsbakken informed the consortium about the diagnostics meeting that took place earlier that March, which aimed to clarify the process's goals. Then, he briefly described the relevant indicators and also mentioned some issues with convergence due to high GHG prices. In this context, he, Dr Mittal and Dr Glen Peters (CICERO) had a short discussion on the sensitivity scenarios on non-CO₂ price ratios, with Dr Mittal stressing the need to figure indicators for non-CO₂ prices. Furthermore, Dr Alaa Al Khourdajie (Imperial) and Dr Mittal discussed how the vetting process affects the database releases from the IPCC between Assessment Reports, with Dr Al Khourdajie mentioning the IIASA plans to release annual data.</p> <p>Lastly, Ms. Frilingou informed the partners that there is an online</p>	<p>Run models for validation checks</p> <p>Communicate with NTUA administration to link task output to the platform</p>	<p>All modelling partners</p> <p>All task leaders</p>

	Excel file for Tasks and their links to the platform, requesting that task leaders communicate with NTUA administration for this issue.		
WP4	Next, Dr Al Khourdajie and Ms. Noelia Ferreras Alonso (CARTIF) discussed the progress of Task 4.1, stressing the need for more useful guidelines for scenarios, with Ms. Ferreras Alonso proposing to plan a meeting with modelling teams. Regarding the remaining Tasks Dr Mittal and Dr Al Khourdajie stated that were already covered from the previous conversations.		
WP5	Next, Dr-Dirk Jan van de Ven took the floor to present the progress on Task 5.6. He mentioned that BC3 will send an e-mail the following week and that the first results of the SDG mapping will be available at the beginning of April. Next, Mr Gonzalo Parrado Hernando (CARTIF) briefly presented the work on WILIAM. Then, Dr Korsbakken started a discussion on land-use parameters needed for other models, mentioning that he will send a follow-up e-mail. Nevertheless, he also suggested that partners communicate with him for further guidance. In this context, he and Dr Gardumi had a discussion on what type of data will be needed.		
WP6	Next, Dr Gardumi continued by proceeding to WP6, mentioning the progress of modelling in the case study countries. Specifically, RUSL partners are developing a CLEWs model, and Ukrainian partners are working on an OSeMOSYS model, which will be ready in April. On the other hand, modelling for Ethiopia has not started yet and TUM partners are focusing on the modelling classes, in which they are doing a great job. Moreover, he briefed the consortium on the progress and timeline of Task 6.4. Following Dr Gardumi, Ms. Sophia Theodoropoulou (UPRC) took the floor, informing the partners that there is good progress in most KPIs but she also stressed the need to further focus on the website and platform, for which she presented a set of actions. She also mentioned that the download rate of training materials must be improved. Furthermore, she encouraged all partners to engage with the project's posts on its social media accounts. Lastly, she presented the monitoring process of social media activity and showcased its expected outcomes and actions. Ms. Natasha Frilingou ended the meeting by thanking everyone for participating.		

2.7 Executive Board Meeting – 18 June 2024

2.7.1 Agenda

Executive Board Meeting
Tuesday, 18 June, 2024
14:00-15:00 CEST

Microsoft Teams ([Link](#))

Participants: All Partners

Agenda

1. Update on project progress (completed, ongoing, upcoming tasks & deliverables)
 - WP1: Project Management
 - Feedback on the mid-term review (WP leads, NTUA)
 - Finding hosts for next physical GA meeting (October 2024) (All!)
 - ECEMP submissions (July 2024)
 - WP2: Listening
 - 1st PRM survey results (Bruegel, Study leads)
 - 2nd PRM: Policy Steering Groups, timeline (Bruegel)
 - WP3: Exchanging
 - Task 3.2 – Model linking (Aalto)
 - Task 3.6 – Open science protocols (BC3)
 - WP4: Modelling
 - Task 4.1 – From policy needs to scenario frameworks – Update (CARTIF)
 - Task 4.3 – Broad scenario logic update (CICERO)
 - WP5: Expanding
 - Gathering all modelling outputs from RP1 (NTUA)
 - WP6: Explaining
 - Task 6.4 – Drivers, barriers, and policy analysis progress (WI)
 - D6.6 (Aug 2024)
 - Task 6.5 – Progress on case study country workshops & models (KTH, KEI, TUM, RUSL, AAiT)
 - D6.7 (Aug 2024)
2. Any other business

2.7.2 Minutes

Present on Call	Name and Surname	Organisation
1	Natasha Frilingou	NTUA
2	Anastasios Karamaneas	NTUA
3	Alexandros Nikas	NTUA
4	Ilkka Keppo	Aalto
5	Ghadaksaz Hesam	Aalto
6	Rasmus Magni Johanssen	AAU
7	Dirk-Jan van de Ven	BC3
8	Russell Horowitz	BC3
9	Claudia Rodés	BC3
10	Jon Sampedro	BC3
11	Adrián Lauer	Bruegel
12	Adrián Mateo Martínez	CARTIF
13	Noelia Ferreras Alonso	CARTIF
14	Jan Ivar Korsbakken	CICERO
15	Shivika Mittal	CICERO
16	Panagiotis Fragkos	E3M
17	Anastasis Giannousakis	E3M
18	Chamindie Senaratne	KTH
19	Francesco Gardumi	KTH
20	Camilla Lo Giudice	KTH
21	Nikolaos Kleanthis	UPRC
22	Sophia Theodoropoulou	UPRC
23	Vasilis Stavrakas	UPRC
24	Jyoti Maheshwari	IIMA
25	Solomon Teferi	AAiT
26	Lorenzo Rinaldi	POLIMI
27	Alaa Al Khourdajie	Imperial

Minutes: Main issues discussed

Item	Description	Action	
		What	Who
WP1	<p>Dr Nikas (NTUA) started the meeting by informing all partners on the outcome of the midterm review, thanking WP leads for their great presentations during the meeting.</p> <p>Next, Dr Nikas asked which WP lead could host the next GA among Imperial, KTH and Bruegel, which ideally should happen in October, suggesting either Imperial or KTH with Dr Alaa Al Khourdajie (Imperial) & Dr Francesco Gardumi (KTH) replying that they would communicate with their institutes and get back.</p> <p>Then, IAMC and ECEMP submissions were discussed, and Dr Nikas reminded the partners of the deadlines.</p> <p>And finally, an application for a side event in COP29 was discussed, to which Imperial & CICERO confirmed that they could apply, as NTUA is not a Party / observer organisation.</p>	<p>Submission of financial reports</p> <p>Follow up on GA hosts & scope availability</p>	<p>All partners</p> <p>NTUA, Imperial, KTH & Bruegel</p>
WP2	<p>Then, Mr Adrian Lauer (Bruegel) took the floor to briefly update the partners on the status of the Policy Response Mechanism. Several meetings are being organised with Policy Steering Groups, leading to a set of policy questions documented in the upcoming deliverable D2.3.</p>		

WP3	Dr Ilkka Keppo (Aalto) took the floor, focusing on an upcoming publication related to model linking and Task 3.1. He has collected expressions of interest and will now assign section leads, and the goal is to finalise it by October.		
WP4	Mr Adrián Mateo (CARTIF) updated the partners on Task 4.1, and the distribution of work for each section of the deliverable, to be submitted by the end of August. Then, Dr Jan Ivar Korsbakken (CICERO) focused on the Broad Scenario Logic to be submitted early July, and the update of the validation tool. Dr Shivika Mittal added that CICERO has been collecting the update of climate policies and National Determined Contributions (NDCs) in time for the 2 nd PRM cycle.		
WP5	Dr Panagiotis Fragkos (E3M) informed the consortium that D5.8 - Climate action in the sustainability spectrum has been submitted in time. In terms of future tasks, E3M will meet with modelling teams to discuss necessary modelling enhancement for the 2 nd cycle of the project, while Task 5.7 A novel approach to 'expanded multi-model assessment' has slowly kicked-off, and will require modelling results from all the studies conducted during the 1 st PRM in a common format.	Gather 1 st PRM results in IPCC format	NTUA & E3M
WP6	Dr Gardumi focused on the modelling progress in case study countries as part of Task 6.5, and the modelling classes in Kenya which will soon come to an end. Regarding Task 6.4, he flagged that country studies are also progressing albeit a bit slower than anticipated, but the deliverable will still be submitted on time. Finally, regarding our CDE strategy, we would need to focus on synergistic/ joint events as 4 more events need to be held by the end of the project. Ms. Sophia Theodoropoulou (UPRC) added that newsletter recipients should also increase, and congratulated the partners on a very successful roll-out of the IAM COMPACT training kit, which achieved >400 download so far.		
Any other business	The ICTP Summer School in Trieste was also discussed, as Dr Gardumi and Ms. Salsabilah Abdulhalim (TUM) will represent IAM COMPACT as trainers. Dr Gardumi informed the partners that this year, a new session focusing on train the trainers will be added, and the agenda is well connected to the capacity development work of IAM COMPACT.		

3 Scientific Advisory Board meetings

The SAB serves as an advisory body to the IAM COMPACT Consortium. The General Assembly (GA), which includes the Project Coordinator and one representative from each beneficiary, is responsible for selecting and appointing SAB members. The initial formulation, tentative composition, and Terms of Reference for the SAB were documented in the first milestone of IAM COMPACT (scheduled for completion in Month 2). NTUA, in collaboration with all partners, had reached out to various stakeholders, including academics and climate change mitigation experts, to invite them to join the project's SAB. The SAB currently consists of nine members, but its composition may change in response to new opportunities and challenges.

As in this period only one General Assembly took place (February 2024) and SAB members in particular were eventually unable to join as a last-minute change of dates was required to accommodate emerging needs, there were limited interactions with the SAB in the context of these regular meetings. However, NTUA shared with the SAB a very detailed slide deck showcasing the project's progress, as well as a series of emails updating them on several key developments, achievements, and challenges—to which the feedback was positive.

Nonetheless, apart from systematically exchanging material with and requesting feedback from the members of the SAB in the last year of the project, we plan to interact with the SAB in the upcoming 4th GA meeting of the project (September 2024) in another dedicated session, which should typically fall within this period (August 2024) but was postponed due to summer holidays—as well as in the two such GA meetings of the final year of IAM COMPACT.